

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF INCREASING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN THE GROWING OF COTTON RAW MATERIALS

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Abstract. The article discusses the issues of increasing economic efficiency in cotton growing in the current global economic environment.

Key words: economic efficiency, profitability, key indicators, system, profit, material cost, income, cultivated area, gross product, productivity.

INTRODUCTION. The cotton complex plays an important role in the process of socio-economic development, and it is of great importance for the economy of the country, which dominates its successful development. Cotton products processed in factories are very important raw materials for the light and food industry. Cotton products are also used in heavy industry. Up to 300 types of consumer products and technical products are made from cotton raw materials. In the economy of our country, the weight of cotton growing and cotton ginning industry is large. As the industry develops, other sectors of the national economy will also develop. From this point of view, further development of cotton growing is considered one of the priorities of our republic. It is known that our country has long been famous for its climate, senmiun soil, underground and surface resources. Currently, 3.0-3.2 million tons of raw cotton are grown in our country every year. The main factor for achieving such success is the constant attention paid to the industry by our government, especially economic incentives, scientific and technical achievements, and the introduction of advanced technologies, a great deal of farming activity. is the opening of the road. Thanks to the gradual reforms, the material and technical base of farms is getting stronger year by year. It is known that our republic occupies the sixth place among the more than 80 major cotton-growing countries in the world in terms of cotton cultivation area, and produces an average of 3-4% of the cotton grown in the world.

However, the average yield of cotton per hectare in the republic is 30-35 s/ha and remains much lower compared to the indicators of foreign countries in this regard. For example, the yield in Turkey is 70 s/ha. Therefore, eliminating some of the negative results observed in the cotton growing sub-complex, bringing the efficiency of this industry to the level of advanced countries, finding solutions to the problems of increasing cotton yield and soil fertility is a necessary condition for ensuring the competitiveness of the industry in the domestic and international markets.

It is known that fertile land and water resources are limited. Improving the efficiency of using existing resources? First of all, it is achieved by increasing the productivity of each hectare of cotton. Productivity increase is related to high-quality and short-term execution of agrotechnological processes, as well as the application of innovative and digital technologies to the field.

One of the main directions of the effective development of the cotton industry in Uzbekistan is the full implementation of the legal basis of the reform of agrarian and economic relations in the countryside. During the years of independence, more than 180 normative legal documents were adopted in the agricultural sector of the country in order to increase their efficiency. In addition, about 500 regulatory legal documents related to the agricultural sector with some features are in effect.

In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 6, 2020 "On measures to introduce market principles in the field of cotton production", the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan The decision of June 22, 2020 "On measures to further develop cotton-textile production", the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's decision of June 27, 2020 "Measures to improve the system of testing and certification of agricultural and reclamation techniques" on activities", Decree No. PF-5853 of October 23, 2019 "On approval of the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030", Decisions of March 25, 2022 "On measures to support the introduction of new irrigation technologies and increase soil fertility and productivity in cotton fields" were adopted. In order to ensure the implementation of these decisions, extensive and serious reforms are being carried out in the agriculture of our country. In particular, the state order for cotton and grain was abandoned and pricing was liberalized. Product production was switched to a cluster system and all conditions were created for their development. The goal is to dramatically increase output, create high added value and new jobs, and most importantly, increase income and interest.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. A number of leading agrarian economists and theoreticians of our republic, including: A.A.Abdug'aniev, A.A.Shokirov, A.Joraev, A.Z.Zokirov, A.S.Samutali, D.Q.Ahmedov, N.S. Khushmatov, R.V. Abdullaev, R.Kh. Khusanov, F.Q.Qayumov, F.Kh.Nazarova, CH.M.Murodov, E.J.Yusupov, O'.P.Umurzakov, Q.A.Khasanjanov, Q.A.Choriev and others conducted scientific research.

RESULTS. Today, the cotton fields are connected to full clusters, and although the state purchase price has increased by 3.5 times and is close to the world market prices, the profit does not reach the expected level. In fact, it was assumed that the textile sector will be the leader in the new stage of reforms in the country's economy. However, the amount of exports in the industry did not even reach 2 billion dollars. The reason for this is the increase in the cost of raw materials, the deterioration of the financial situation of yarn-producing enterprises, and the shallowness of the economic mechanism aimed at releasing the finished product to the world market. As a result of the increase in the state purchase price for cotton raw materials, one ton of raw materials costs 2,000 dollars to a primary processing enterprise, and the price of 1 ton of yarn on the world market is on average 2,500 dollars. During processing, 10 percent of fiber is lost and profitability decreases. If we take into account the costs of processing cotton, the level of profitability will further decrease, which will be a serious obstacle for the development of textile industry enterprises.

According to calculations, the productivity can be increased to 38-40 centners per hectare by applying modern management system and innovative technologies for the development of cotton cultivation. In this case, when raw materials grown on 800,000 hectares are processed and sold as ready-made knitted products, the annual net profit will increase to at least 1.5 billion dollars.

The profitability of cotton cultivation in the countries of the world has remained unchanged over the past few years. This includes the global climate change occurring on our planet, environmental stress factors for cotton cultivation - excessive rainfall during the planting period, temperature increase during the flowering stage, decrease in soil fertility, increase in pest and disease groups, lack of agrotechnologies against resource shortages, etc. problems have a negative impact. In this regard, measures such as solving these problems in cotton farming, increasing the efficiency of the use of resources used in cotton farming, and introducing innovative, resource-saving technologies to the network should be implemented. Effective use of resources in the cotton industry of our country, activities that increase the efficiency of the implementation of resource-saving technologies are considered issues of state importance. For example, in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the priority task is to increase the income of peasants and farmers by at least 2 times, to bring the annual growth of agriculture to at least 5% through the intensive development of agriculture on a scientific basis. It was also noted that there are no effective mechanisms for the economic stimulation of the introduction of water-saving technologies in cotton farming, and the lack of effective state support mechanisms for local producers who provide components for drip irrigation systems. From this point of view, expanding the scope of scientific research in the direction of increasing the efficiency of the introduction of resource-saving technologies in cotton farming is an urgent issue.

One of the main requirements of the current period is not only the production of raw materials in agriculture, including cotton, but also the correct and effective implementation of its processing and sale. Because the main part of the added value created, that is, the income, is formed in the following areas. In our republic, the issues of using cotton raw materials, cotton fiber, cotton oil, gas and other cotton products have been solved separately. However, starting from 2017, the formation of the cotton-textile cluster puts on the agenda to solve the issues of increasing the efficiency of the multi-stage complex system in the process from plowing the land to planting, care and production of finished products from raw materials.

It is important to increase economic efficiency in cotton farming, to determine efficiency indicators, and to develop appropriate conclusions based on their assessment. Research on increasing the economic efficiency of production has been researched by a number of theoretical and practical scientists of our country as a general economic problem. In particular, according to A. Abdug'aniev, the concepts of "efficiency" and "economic efficiency" exist in economics. They can be determined by country, sector, enterprise, directions and some products. The concept of economic efficiency has a wider meaning than the concept of efficiency. Economic efficiency means the costs associated with activities carried out during a year (in a certain period) are compared with the amount of net profit obtained as a result of them. Then, the higher the amount of net profit received in return for the expenses, the higher the level of economic efficiency, and vice versa. Efficiency is represented by the progress achieved as a result of one or another event, work, and production of products.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it can be noted that the development of the cotton complex, which is of decisive importance for the country's economy in modern economic conditions, gives a strong impetus to the development of raw materials production and industrial sectors. This is also evident in the experience of developed countries. From this point of view, encouraging the development of the cotton complex and increasing its competitiveness is important for the national economic interests of our country. Support for

the development of the cotton complex can become the basis for the development of other structural complexes of the national economy.

Increasing economic efficiency in cotton farming is related to the following factors:

- the requirement of fertile, flat lands for cotton cultivation and the necessity of strict adherence to the agrotechnology of cotton cultivation, feeding, watering and processing;
- elimination of seasonality in labor organization and provision of labor resources with uniform and full employment throughout the year;
- changes in the demand for cotton fiber in the world market, the need to collect cotton in a short period of time, etc.
- determination of the ratio of organic and mineral fertilizers necessary for the implementation of agrotechnical activities, timely implementation of irrigation works according to the established standards, as well as the selection of fruitful, promising cotton varieties resistant to various diseases in the cross-section of regions placement;
- to achieve proportionality of the amount of financial resources and the prices of infrastructures in farms and to take measures to ensure cost savings for cotton care;
- increasing labor productivity by increasing the qualification and retraining of specialist employees, workers and employees, using the mechanism of financial incentives for them;
- to ensure effective use of drip or intermittent irrigation methods in the conditions of increasing water scarcity.

As a result of the research, indicators representing the efficiency of cotton cultivation were systematized. These indicators allow to assess the effectiveness of the use of all types of resources in the field, covering the relevant macroeconomic indicators. As a result of the implemented measures, it is necessary to express the economic efficiency of the farm in the form of natural, value, relative and quality indicators.

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